

Species 1: *H. besckei*

NOT test

Species 2: *H. ethilla*

Environmental overlap

Equivalency

Niche Similarity:
D = 0.426

Background 2→1

Background 1→2

Species 1: *H. besckei*

PC1, PNT.index: 0.01; minimm PNT

NDT test

Species 2: *H. ethilla*

PC1, PNT.index: 0.61; high PNT

Environmental overlap

PC1
Red=S1>S2, Blue=S1<S2, Cor. Uncorrected= 0.425

Equivalency

Niche Similarity:
D = 0.623

Background 2->1

Background 1->2

